

IMPROVING ENGLISH LANGUAGE SKILLS IN MEDICAL FIELD CONTEXT

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Abstract. *The study examines ways to increase the productivity of learning English in a medical context, which allow students of medical universities to improve their language acquisition. The methodological base, based on various aspects of innovative and pedagogical approaches, helps to diversify learning. Besides, visual aids are discussed as suitable tools for teaching English in medical context. The importance of mastering four basic language skills - speaking, listening comprehension, writing and reading in the process of contextual learning of the English language is also considered.*

Key words: *English, teacher, methodology, student, approach, interaction, medical, speaking, listening, writing, reading.*

Introduction. Situational context, as a way to productivity in language learning, creates a certain system of communication and relationships, and allows the learner to understand the semantic side of speech material. It is an arrangement of the interaction between certain factors that involve people into a communicative situation. When teaching a language, real objects or realities are used, which make it possible to intellectually perceive the context. The real situation within the medical context, such as dialogues various events, watching videos, role-playing games as well as the use of drawings, slides, diagrams, graphs and others are perceived as a rich source of methodological basis. Such realities add variety to the learning process. Therefore, mastering lexical units not separately, when only their meanings are given, but in the most real and natural conditions, that is, in a situational context, gives the greatest results, elevating the meaning of the language and motivating for its further study of language.

The medical situational context is the method that involves learning a language by including the different professional situations in the language learning. The advantage of the situational context is the dominance of specialized themes in speech, the use of medical training tools and concentration on the topic which is currently of a great interest for the students. It gives an opportunity to deep insight into the specialty. The effectiveness of the GT of it lies in the fact that the students have already studied this topic in classes on specialized subjects in medicine. This is an important motivational moment for them and it is possible to learn language structures in a traditional context from rules to examples due to the systematization of the material in the native language. This method, as one of the time-tested methods, can be effective if it is correctly selected according to the level of the learners, taking into account their cognitive abilities.

Methods and research. Thinking of a situation on developing a pair role-play, it is possible to present a contextual lesson plan, which implies a dialogue between doctor and patient (Table 1). In this case, the points of the lesson organization, the use of equipment, lesson aims, learning outcomes and assessment methods are considered.

Table 1. Organization of lesson on contextual language learning

Organization of the lesson	
Topic of lesson: Doctor and patient	Lesson Aims (teacher’s aim): • To evaluate knowledge and use of basic vocabulary on health and medicine
Materials and equipment required: Electrical and electronic teaching aids Computer and projector, board, worksheets, realia	Learning Outcomes. At the end of the lesson, the students should be able to: · Identify/revise lexical items on used within situation · Facilitate listening and speaking skills
Strategies for introduction of new words, consolidation of new words: brainstorming, pair work, group work	Assessment methods (how learning outcomes will be assessed): Teacher observation/ peer observation and feedback

It should be noted that while teaching and learning English, it is impossible to cover the whole language, so according to certain requirements the appropriate material, direction and methodology are selected. The learning of English language occurs during contextual moments, and the success of mastering depends on abilities, the effectiveness of teaching methods, and many other factors. However, the given process is still different from the traditional methods based on learning grammar rules and vocabulary, and it is carried out more naturally. The reasons and goals for contextual learning are very important as they imply teaching activity and professional development, and require a special approach. Also, a lot depends on the desire, objectives and the tasks the learner sets for himself.

During contextual learning visual aids are valuable tools for language teachers as they help enhance comprehension, retention, and engagement among learners. There are many visual aids available to teachers of foreign languages. There is a wide range of them, such as interactive whiteboards, pictures, images, videos, graphic organizers, flashcards, charts, graphs and others. Currently, the methodology of language teaching shows a variety of ways to use them in the classroom, taking into account their suitability for different types of learners. So, we will try to discuss the use and suitability of some of them in teaching foreign languages.

1. Pictures and Images.

Suitability: Pictures and images are effective for visual learners who benefit from concrete visual representations. *The usage:* Teachers can use pictures and images to introduce vocabulary, describe scenes, tell stories, and spark discussions. Learners can also create picture-based presentations or stories to practice speaking and writing skills.

2. Videos and Multimedia Content.

Suitability: Videos and multimedia content appeal to auditory and visual learners who prefer dynamic and interactive materials. *The usage:* Teachers can use videos to demonstrate language usage, cultural practices, authentic conversations, and real-life scenarios. The learners can watch videos with subtitles, engage in role-plays, and discuss content in groups.

3. Graphic Organizers.

Suitability: Graphic organizers are beneficial for visual learners who need structure and organization in their learning. *The usage:* Teachers can use graphic organizers such as mind maps, Venn diagrams, and concept maps to organize information, outline essays, summarize texts, and compare ideas. Learners can use graphic organizers for note-taking and brainstorming activities.

4. Interactive Whiteboards.

Suitability: Interactive whiteboards are suitable for learners who benefit from interactive and technology-enhanced learning experiences. *The usage:* Teachers can use interactive whiteboards to display multimedia content, write notes, play interactive games, and facilitate collaborative learning activities. Learners can interact with the whiteboard to practice vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation.

In the process of teaching as well as learning a foreign language, all these various visual aids can be applied to students of all levels of language proficiency. Teachers should evaluate the needs and preferences of the learners and select visual aids accordingly in order to effectively enhance learning outcomes.

During contextual English language learning in medical topic, we cannot give exact answer to the question of how many rules or grammar exercises should be given. It is impossible to give a complete description of English language with all grammatical rules. The development of professional relations requires English language to conform to its new functions, improvement and structural adaptation, including the grammar, too. The evolution of English language is a constant process, with continuous change and reproduction of its forms and content. Here the teacher's activity is aimed at improving and activating the cognitive activity of the student, taking into account the accounting of time, resources and the content of the lesson (Table 2). English teacher must do everything to make the student feel confident during study time, create a natural and friendly atmosphere in the classroom with the teacher and groupmates. Professional context is needed in teaching activities when much attention is paid to grammatical units, vocabulary, translation, as well as speaking, writing, reading and listening skills.

Table 2. Lesson Plan on contextual learning

Duration	Content	Teacher Activity	Learner Activity	Resources
5 min	Register and welcome	Welcome Register Overview of content	Listens and answer on questions	Electrical and electronic teaching aids
10 min	Whole group revision brainstorm of vocabulary on theme: Health and Patient)	Facilitates activity and feedback: writes ideas on board (teacher may nominate students to do this)	Gives feedback of ideas and suggestions	Whiteboard
10 min	Introduction of new vocabulary by using presentation of realia (phonendoscope, medical uniform, tools, etc.)	Explains and facilitates the new lexical material with real things, giving students to touch and look at them.	Write the new words and definitions, have opportunity to touch realia	Realia Medical tools

It is important to master four basic language skills: speaking, listening comprehension, writing and reading. Conversational speech is needed to communicate with other people, and properly delivered speech is always a direct path to success. Listening performs the function of mutual understanding between the listener and the speaker, to understand speech and to do the job correctly. Most of the professional work includes writing various letters, information, reports, etc., so writing skills for the functioning in a foreign language are very important. Reading is also a significant component of any activity, so it is important to be able to improve this skill.

It is known that speaking is an important language skill than writing, because it promotes communication and expression of one's thoughts. With the help of speaking, students can effectively interact with each other professionally. Teaching students spelling promotes reading skills, and improves language learning. Frequent writing helps to understand what they read. Experts say that the most effective way to assess students' knowledge is to give them an assignment to write a particular task. While writing, there is a better understanding of study material. Therefore, teaching students to write English is also a necessary condition for learning the language. Consequently, speaking and writing are equally important in teaching students who learn English. A balanced approach to both skills is an important component of the teaching strategy.

Creating a pair dialogue as a "Doctor and patient" role game, students consolidate the new vocabulary while preparation the phrases for such dialogues, as: "What's problem?", "I have a stomach ache", "There is prescription of tablets", "You should take diagnostic tests" and others, the teacher develops their speech and communication within the specialty. That process usually takes place in many stages: while making sentences the students master grammar and vocabulary, as well speaking and other language abilities.

Conclusion. Contextualization in professional sphere is necessary for the medical students in English language learning. In this way, he can master not only language, but a specialty as well. They communicates in constant medical practice in the language, developing such abilities as interaction and working correctly in the language.

A person can learn a great number of words in a foreign language, master grammar well, but at the same time it is necessary to develop speech skills as well. They need a contextual support to use it in their activity. Interactivity and the ability to adapt to the professional environment, communication skills, the capability to attract people's attention, negotiate, write and respond to letters and documents, read and process information – all this must be learnt to function effectively in English language. A lot depends on the language abilities of the learner. Teacher's qualification, timely involvement in the language environment, competent approach, methods, procedures and techniques in the teaching determine the main priorities in any language learning.

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